

A Novel Synthesis of Yohimbane Skeleton¹—Synthesis of 17,18-Dimethoxy-15,16,17,18,19,20-hexadehydroyohimbane by Condensation of an Indolylethylbromide with 3(2H)-isoquinolone

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Treatment of 6,7-dimethoxy-3-isochromanone with hydrazine followed by hydrochloric acid afforded 1,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxy-3(2H)-isoquinolone. Condensation of the isoquinolone with 2,3'-indolylethylbromide afforded the tetracyclic lactam which on phosphoryl chloride cyclization followed by sodium borohydride reduction gave the title compound in good yield, thereby providing an interesting entry to the yohimbane skeleton.

WE recently reported some convenient syntheses of the berbine alkaloids² employing the 3-isochromanones³ and the bromo esters⁴ derived from them. The 3-isochromanones has also been used successfully to synthesize the yohimbane alkaloids⁵. The most recent of the versatile uses of the 3-isochromanones made by us is the berbine synthesis being the condensation of the phenethyl bromide with 3(2H)-isoquinolone derived from 3-isochromanone. The present method of yohimbane synthesis essentially parallels the berbine synthesis⁶, yet the significance of this method lies in the fact that it constitutes the first report of yohimbane alkaloid synthesis by this newly evolved reaction sequence. This method has the added advantage of placing the desired¹ substitution on rings A and E of the yohimbane⁷ and also easy feasibility⁸ of the intermediates (Scheme 1).

2,3'-indolylethylbromide⁷ (III) (225 mg) and 1,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxy-3(2H)-isoquinolone⁸ (II) (195 mg) in absolute ethanol (12 ml) was added anhydrous K₂CO₃ (50 mg) and KI (10 mg). The mixture was refluxed under stirring at 100° for 32 hr, cooled, the solvent removed *in vacuo* and the residue diluted with excess water. The solution was extracted with CHCl₃ and the extract washed with water, dried and distilled. The residue crystallized from MeOH to give tetracyclic lactam (IV) as powder (160 mg, 50%), m.p. 74°; ir (CHCl₃), 1640 (six membered lactam), 3330 cm⁻¹. Found: C, 71.8; H, 5.9; N, 8.1. C₂₁H₂₁N₂O₃ requires C, 72.0; H, 6.28; N, 8.0%

17,18-Dimethoxy-15,16,17,18,19,20-hexadehydro-yohimbane (V): Freshly distilled POCl₃ (2.0 ml) was added to a solution of the lactam (IV) (350 mg)

Scheme 1

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Wilmad (WCV 60) spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. Solutions were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

2-(2, 3'-Indolylethyl)-6,7-dimethoxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-3(2H)-isoquinolone (IV): To a solution of

in dry benzene (10 ml) and the solution was refluxed at 100° for 2.5 hr. The residue left after removal of the excess reagent and the solvent was treated with an excess of ice, the organic materials extracted in CHCl₃ and solvent removed *in vacuo* to leave a syrup. The syrup was dissolved in MeOH (7 ml) and treated with NaBH₄ (120mg) in portions during 30 min. After refluxing for 1 hr the solvent was removed, residue diluted with water and extracted with CHCl₃. Removal of the solvent and crystallization

from MeOH gave the compound (V) (155 mg, 47%), m.p. 250-51° (lit.⁹, m.p. 249-50°); ir (KBr) 3335 cm⁻¹; nmr [(CD₃)₂SO] δ : 10.7 (broad, 1H, -NH), 7.5-6.8 (m, 4H, C-9H; C-10H; C-11H and C-12H), 6.75 (s, 2H, C-16H and C-19H), 4.2-4.0 (m, 1H, C-3H), 3.86 (broad, 2H, C-21H), 3.75 and 3.74 (2s, 6H, -OCH₃), 3.8-2.8 (m, 6H, C-5H, C-6H and C-14H). Found: C, 74.9; H, 6.2; N, 8.1. C₂₁H₂₂N₂O₂ requires C, 75.1; H, 6.5; N, 8.3%.

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